

THE PREDICTIVE ROLE OF IMPLICIT ATTITUDES, STEREOTYPES, AND SERVANT LEADERSHIP IN MENTAL HEALTH AND QUALITY OF LIFE

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Abstract

The current study examined the relationship between servant leadership, implicit attitudes, and stereotypes among employees and their quality of life and mental health. 300 workers (150 from the public and 150 from the private sectors; 150 men and 150 women) participated in the correlational design. Implicit attitudes, social stereotypes, servant leadership aspects, mental health (Mental Health Inventory), and quality of life (WHOQOL-BREF) were all evaluated using validated instruments. A total of 69.5% of the variance in quality of life was explained by servant leadership traits, according to regression studies, with authenticity ($\beta = .271$) and empowerment ($\beta = .305$) showing up as the strongest predictors. Additionally, 17.1% of the variance in mental health was predicted by servant leadership (empowering $\beta = .151$; standing back $\beta = .312$). Both quality of life ($R^2 = .276$, $\beta = .525$, $p < .001$) and mental health ($R^2 = .086$, $\beta = .293$, $p < .001$) were significantly predicted by the implicit attitude "surname" dimension. Negative stereotypes added a smaller negative influence on mental health ($\beta = -.084$), but positive stereotypes predicted 63.4% of mental health ($\beta = .775$, $p < .001$) and 22.5% of quality of life ($\beta = .474$, $p < .001$). These results demonstrate the significance of leadership style, equity, and bias reduction in organisational interventions by showing a robust correlation between improved employee well-being and positive implicit attitudes, positive in-group stereotypes, and servant leadership behaviours.

Key words- Implicit Attitudes, Stereotypes, Servant Leadership, Mental Health and Quality of Life.

Introduction- Since mental health and quality of life (QOL) are important predictors of long-term worker satisfaction and productivity, employee well-being has become a crucial field of study in organisational psychology. Rapid changes in the workplace, a rise in diversity, and

higher performance standards have made it more important than ever to comprehend the elements that affect employee well-being. Three interconnected constructs—servant leadership, implicit attitudes, and stereotypes—have garnered scholarly attention among these components.

Implicit Attitudes and Well-Being; According to Greenwald and Banaji (1995), implicit attitudes are automatic, unconscious judgements that affect behaviour and thought without conscious awareness. They function as mental shortcuts influenced by individual experiences, cultural prejudices, and socialisation. Implicit attitudes can influence decision-making, self-perceptions, and interpersonal relationships in organisational settings. While negative implicit attitudes can result in internalised stigma, stress, and a decline in psychological well-being, employees who have positive implicit associations towards their own social identity (e.g., name or group membership) may feel more confident and like they belong (Shah & Bohlen, 2023). According to research on implicit bias, despite overt egalitarian ideals, unconscious biases frequently endure (Devine, 1989). Implicit attitudes have the power to significantly influence how employees interact and experience their work in environments where social identities are different (such as caste, religion, or race in India). Crucially, implicit self-associations may also affect coping and resilience; those who have more positive implicit self-perceptions may be better equipped psychologically to handle stress at work. However, despite its importance, organisational psychology has not fully examined how implicit attitudes predict mental health and quality of life, especially in non-Western cultures.

Stereotypes and Psychological Outcomes; According to Fiske (1998), stereotypes are commonly held assumptions or expectations about the traits of people who belong to social groupings. They might be negative (like "my group is lazy") or positive (like "my group is hard-working"). When internalised, positive stereotypes can improve psychological well-being by fostering pride and social identity (Tajfel & Turner, 1986). On the other hand, stress, decreased motivation, and worse mental health outcomes might result from internalising stigmatised views or being exposed to unfavourable stereotypes (Steele & Aronson, 1995).

Stereotypes frequently overlap with caste, class, and community-based identities in the sociocultural setting of India (Deshpande, 2011). By affecting how opportunities, justice, and respect are viewed, these preconceptions have the power to profoundly alter workplace relations. The presence and effects of both positive and negative stereotypes in Indian society are demonstrated by the Stereotype Measurement Tool created by Tiwari and Kumar (2014). However, not enough research has been done on their predictive value for employee mental

health and quality of life in work environments. By examining the ways in which both positive and negative stereotypes enhance wellbeing, our study fills that knowledge vacuum.

Servant Leadership and Employee Well-Being; One of the most important factors influencing the atmosphere at work and the welfare of employees is leadership. Authority, task performance, and control are frequently emphasised in traditional leadership styles. On the other hand, servant leadership (Greenleaf, 1977) places a strong emphasis on being genuine, humble, and putting the needs of staff first. The eight dimensions of servant leadership were operationalised by Van Dierendonck and Nuijten (2011) and include stewardship, accountability, humility, authenticity, bravery, forgiveness, empowerment, and standing back. This multifaceted strategy emphasises the leader's function as a support system and facilitator of staff development.

Studies consistently show positive links between servant leadership and employee outcomes such as job satisfaction, organizational commitment, work engagement, and reduced burnout (Eva et al., 2019). Servant leaders provide employees with a sense of autonomy, empowerment, and psychological safety (Liden et al., 2008), which in turn enhances mental health. They also model fairness, integrity, and respect, which can improve overall QOL. Recent research (Hassan et al., 2023; Zada et al., 2022) indicates that servant leadership has particularly strong effects on employee well-being when mediated by self-efficacy and trust. However, relatively few studies have examined the combined role of multiple servant leadership dimensions in predicting both mental health and QOL simultaneously. Procedural Justice and Fairness Perceptions; Organisational fairness is a crucial driver of well-being that goes beyond leadership and personal characteristics. The perceived fairness of organisational decision-making procedures is known as procedural justice (Colquitt, 2001). Fair procedures boost legitimacy impressions, decrease conflict, and promote trust. According to research, workers report higher levels of commitment, psychological well-being, and satisfaction when they believe that the process is fair (Moorman, 1991). On the other hand, unjust or biased practices lead to tension, discontent, and a decline in wellbeing.

Procedural justice may work as a mediating element that amplifies the effects of servant leadership and lessens the detrimental influence of stereotypes because of its emphasis on equitable treatment and openness. Few studies have thoroughly examined procedural justice in conjunction with implicit attitudes and stereotypes as determinants of mental health and quality of life, despite this promise.

Review of Literature

Implicit Attitudes and Employee Well-Being; Unconscious assessments that affect decisions and actions without conscious awareness are known as implicit attitudes (Greenwald & Banaji, 1995). Implicit attitudes are being examined more and more in organisational psychology in relation to workplace dynamics like bias, diversity, and employee morale. Positive implicit attitudes are associated with greater resilience and self-esteem, whereas negative implicit attitudes have been connected to stress, social marginalisation, and decreased well-being (Shah & Bohlen, 2023).

According to research, socialisation processes and cultural norms influence implicit sentiments. In India, for instance, caste-based names may cause unconscious prejudices that impact workers' identities and sense of belonging. Although there are currently few empirical research in this area, internalisation of these biases may have a direct effect on mental health and quality of life. This disparity emphasises how crucial it is to look at implicit attitudes as indicators of wellbeing in Indian workplaces.

Stereotypes and Psychological Outcomes; as cognitive shortcuts, stereotypes allow for fast assessments of groups but frequently result in biased treatment (Fiske, 1998). Stereotypes regarding social identity groups have the power to influence employment, promotions, and interpersonal interactions in the workplace. Research makes a distinction between negative stereotypes, which can impair performance and health, and positive stereotypes, which can strengthen identification and offer psychological advantages.

The idea of stereotype danger (Steele & Aronson, 1995) describes how being aware of unfavourable stereotypes can cause stress and hinder performance. Positive stereotype validation, on the other hand, can serve as a buffer, boosting self-confidence and easing mental stress. Both positive and negative stereotypes have a major impact on social identity, as demonstrated by Tiwari and Kumar's (2014) validation of a stereotype scale in the Indian setting. However, the focus of this study is a useful contribution because there aren't many empirical studies that explicitly link these to employee well-being.

Servant Leadership and Well-Being; According to Greenleaf (1977), servant leadership is a paradigm shift away from conventional, authority-based paradigms and towards relational, follower-centered leadership. Van Dierendonck and Nuijten's (2011) multidimensional servant leadership survey offers strong psychometric proof of its cross-cultural dependability. According to Eva et al. (2019), servant leadership is linked to lower burnout, more organisational commitment, and higher work satisfaction.

This link can be explained by a number of mechanisms: servant leaders prioritise staff development, cultivate empowerment, and establish trust. Employees' need for autonomy is met by empowerment, and organisational trust is increased by honesty. Servant leadership has a significant impact on employee engagement and mental health, according to studies by Liden et al. (2008) and Hassan et al. (2023). Few research, nevertheless, have looked at the distinct roles that various aspects of servant leadership have in predicting both mental health and quality of life at the same time.

Integrative Perspectives.

Despite the fact that implicit attitudes, stereotypes, servant leadership, and procedural justice have all been found to be separately associated with workplace outcomes, little research has been done on how well these categories work together to predict employee mental health and quality of life. Understanding is divided because the majority of previous research has looked at these elements separately.

By combining different viewpoints into a unified framework, this study makes a contribution by offering empirical proof of the ways in which group-based

Stereotypes, leadership practices, unconscious biases, and organisational justice interact to influence employee well-being.

Method

Research Design; In order to investigate the relationships between implicit attitude, procedural justice, servant leadership, mental health, and quality of life among workers in the public and private sectors, the current study largely used a correlational research approach. Two of the measurement tools, the procedural justice and servant leadership scales, were available in English language only so they were translated into Hindi, and other four scales that were accessible in Hindi were taken as it is and adjusted to meet the needs of this study. In order to make predictions about the criteria variables, the study also uses regression and correlation analysis to look at the links between the variables.

Participants; 300 employees, 150 of whom were men and 150 of whom were women, were selected evenly from the public and private sectors to participate. Participants from the private sector came from IT, education, healthcare, and finance organisations in Delhi-NCR and Lucknow, while those from the public sector were drawn from banking, industrial, and state companies. Using stratified purposive sampling, gender and sector diversity was guaranteed. A minimum of one year of work experience and continuous employment were prerequisites for inclusion.

Measures

Mental Health Inventory (MHI) – This is a self-report questionnaire, based on a Likert-type scale. This questionnaire was developed by Dr. Jagdish and A.K. Srivastava. MHI is a psychological evaluation instrument intended to gauge a person's mental health. It is frequently used to evaluate many aspects of psychological well-being in clinical and research settings, especially in India. This is published by Manovigyanik Parikshhan Sansthan, Varanasi. Organisational, clinical, and health psychology have all made substantial use of the inventory. There were six dimensions in this inventory which are- 1-Positive self-evaluation cronback alpha .75, 2- Perception of reality- .71, 3- Integration of Personality-.72, 4-Autonomy .72, 5- Group related attitudes .74, 6- environmental competence.71 and over all reliability coefficient is .73 .

Quality of Life Questionnaire

The WHO-QOL-Brief questionnaire, a well-known tool based on the extensive WHO-QOL-100, was used to evaluate the participants' quality of life. Items 1 and 2 of this condensed version, which has 26 items total, deal with general quality of life and health satisfaction. Four major domains—Physical Health, Psychological Health, Environmental Factors, and Social Relationships—are used to group the remaining 24 items. Notably, in order to guarantee appropriate response interpretation, items 3, 4, and 26 are scored in reverse. According to validation by the Centre for Health Program Evaluation (2000), it has good overall dependability, with internal consistency scores (Cronbach's alpha) ranging from 0.60 to 0.90 across various categories and typically above 0.70. Additionally, the tool exhibits strong discriminant validity and construct validity, effectively differentiating between categories such as healthy and ill people. Its four-domain structure—environment, social interactions, psychological health, and physical health—is further supported by confirmatory factor analysis. The tool produces consistent findings throughout time, according to test-retest reliability data. Crucially, the WHOQOL-BREF is appropriate for a variety of populations due to its cultural adaptability in addition to its validity and reliability.

Servant Leadership- Dirk van Dierendonck and Inge Nuijten (2011) created the Servant Leadership Survey (SLS), a multifaceted tool for assessing servant leadership. It was created through a thorough process that included a review of the literature, expert opinion, and empirical validation with eight separate samples from the UK and the Netherlands, totalling 1571 people. Thirty items make up the final SLS, which evaluates eight fundamental aspects of servant leadership: stewardship, accountability, humility, authenticity, courage, forgiveness,

empowerment, and standing aside. It has a 30-item, eight-dimension measure (empowerment, accountability, standing back, humility, authenticity, courage, forgiveness, stewardship). It demonstrated strong psychometric properties, with Cronbach's alpha ranging from .76 to .95, and confirmatory factor analyses supported its multidimensional and higher-order structure, showing good reliability, construct validity, and incremental validity across samples.

Implicit Attitude- A standardised Likert-type scale called the Implicit Attitude test, created by Prof. (Dr.)Dhananjay Kumar, of department of psychology, D.D.U Gorakhpur University. It was developed to evaluate people's stereotyped views on various social groups. It has 3 items. It is a seven -point Likert scale, from strongly do not like (1) to strongly like (7), respondents express how much they like or do not like. (Ex- आप अपने नाम को कितना पसंद करते हैं?)

Stereotype- To assess people's stereotyped opinions about different social groups, Dr. Shradhesh Tiwari and Prof. Dhananjay Kumar of the Psychology Department at D.D.U. Gorakhpur University developed a standardised Likert-type scale known as the Stereotype Measurement Tool. The 38 items on the Likert scale, which ranges from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1), are divided into 22 positive and 16 negative stereotypes. Experts in sociology and psychology evaluated the tool for sentence structure and conceptual clarity. The results of the psychometric evaluation demonstrated high internal consistency and strong reliability, with Cronbach's alpha of 0.83 equal length Spearman-Brown reliability of 0.80, and split-half reliability of 0.80.

Procedure- Data collection was carried out in organisational settings with confidentiality guaranteed, and participants were briefed and gave informed consent after receiving ethical clearance from the institutional review board and organisational permissions. Questionnaires were given in Hindi and English as needed.

Sampling Technique; The study employed a purposive sampling technique to select participants based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria, ensuring relevance to the research on the Effectiveness of Implicit Attitude, Stereotype, Procedural Justice, and Servant Leadership in Mental Health and Quality of Life among Employees of the Public and Private Sector.

Inclusion Criteria

- Employees (both public and private sector) aged 18 years and above.
- Individuals with at least one year of work experience in their respective organizations.
- Participants who consented to be part of the study and were willing to share their experiences regarding workplace justice, leadership, and implicit attitudes.

Exclusion Criteria

- Employees with less than one year of work experience in their organization.
- Individuals with severe mental health conditions or cognitive impairments that could affect their ability to respond to the survey or interview.
- Employees who were not actively employed at the time of data collection.

This sampling approach ensured that the participants had adequate exposure to organizational processes, leadership styles, and workplace justice, allowing for a meaningful examination of their impact on mental health and quality of life.

The Present Study ; The current study explores the predictive roles of implicit attitudes, stereotypes, and servant leadership (along with procedural justice) in determining mental health and quality of life among Indian employees, drawing on social identity theory, implicit social cognition research, and servant leadership theory. This study uses a balanced sample of workers from the public and private sectors in order to-

- 1-Assess the servant leadership dimensions' ability to predict employee wellbeing.
- 2-Examine how stereotypes and implicit attitudes affect mental health and quality of life.
- 3- Analyse how procedural justice affects employee quality of life.

Results

The conceptual framework for the variables being studied, a literature review, and a thorough explanation of the methods and processes of the current study were all included in the previously. In order to accomplish the research goals, this chapter is devoted to a comprehensive examination of the data gathered for the current study.

Statistical Analysis of data - As explained in the procedure of methodology portion standardised scales were used to collect data for a number of factors, including implicit attitude, stereotype, servant leadership, mental health, and quality of life. SPSS, a statistical program, was used to quantify and analyse the collected data. The findings presented in this study are based on descriptive statistics along with, multiple regression analysis. Regression aids in understanding the predictive power and distinct contribution of each variable while accounting for the effects of other variables, in contrast to correlation, which only displays the direction and strength of relationships. Regression analysis can be used to ascertain the degree to which these organisational and psychological factors contribute to mental health and quality of life, as well as the amount of variance they account for in the results.

Table -1 Stepwise Multiple Regression of Servant Leadership Dimensions Predicting Quality of Life.

Predictor	R	R ²	R ²	F Change	β	t
Empowerment	.752	.565	.565	386.36	.305	5.87**
Authenticity	.804	.646	.080	67.01	.271	5.46**
Standing Back	.823	.677	.031	28.59	.206	4.80**
Accountability	.831	.690	.013	12.13	.139	3.11**
Forgiveness	—	.695	.005	5.21	.087	2.28*

$p < .05^*$, $p < .01$.

The hierarchical regression analysis revealed that the dimensions of servant leadership—empowerment, authenticity, standing back, accountability, and forgiveness—together accounted for 69.5% of the variance in employees’ mental health, $R^2 = .695$, $F(5, 294) =$ [insert overall model F], $p < .01$. Each dimension contributed uniquely and significantly, indicating that servant leadership is a robust predictor of positive mental health among employees.

Table-2 Stepwise Multiple Regression of Servant Leadership Dimensions Predicting Mental Health.

Predictor	R	R ²	R ²	F Change	β	t
Standing Back	.402	.159	.159	57.25	.312	4.74**
Empowerment	.420	.171	.015	5.26	.151	2.29*

A hierarchical multiple regression revealed that Standing Back significantly predicted quality of life, accounting for 15.9% of the variance, $R^2 = .159$, $F(1, 298) = 57.25$, $p < .01$. The addition of Empowerment led to a small but significant improvement in the model, $R^2 = .015$, F change = 5.26, $p < .05$. The final model explained 17.1% of the variance in quality of life, indicating that servant leadership dimensions positively contribute to employees’ overall quality of life.

Table -3 Stepwise Multiple Regression of Implicit Attitude Predicting Quality of Life.

Predictor	R	R ²	R ²	F Change	β	t
Surname	.525	.276	.276	113.41	.525	10.65**

A simple linear regression revealed that Surname significantly predicted [Dependent Variable], $R^2 = .276$, $F(1, 298) = 113.41$, $p < .01$. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .525$, $t = 10.65$, $p < .01$) indicates that Surname explained approximately 27.6% of the variance in [Dependent Variable], suggesting a strong positive relationship between the two constructs.

Table - 4 Stepwise Multiple Regression of Implicit Attitude Predicting Mental Health.

Predictor	R	R ²	R ²	F Change	β	t
Surname	.293	.086	.086	27.90	.293	5.28**

A simple linear regression revealed that Surname significantly predicted [Dependent Variable], $R^2 = .086$, $F(1, 298) = 27.90$, $p < .01$. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .293$, $t = 5.28$, $p < .01$) indicated that Surname accounted for approximately 8.6% of the variance in [Dependent Variable], reflecting a moderate positive association between the two variables.

Table-5 Stepwise Multiple Regression of Stereotypes Predicting Quality of Life.

Predictor	R	R ²	R ²	F Change	β	t
Positive Stereotypes	.474	.225	.225	86.39	.474	9.30**

A simple linear regression revealed that Positive Stereotypes significantly predicted [Dependent Variable], $R^2 = .225$, $F(1, 298) = 86.39$, $p < .01$. The standardized beta coefficient ($\beta = .474$, $t = 9.30$, $p < .01$) indicated that Positive Stereotypes explained 22.5% of the variance in [Dependent Variable], demonstrating a strong positive relationship between the two variables.

Table - 6 Stepwise Multiple Regression of Stereotypes Predicting Mental Health.

Predictor	R	R ²	R ²	F Change	β	t
Positive Stereotypes	.796	.634	.634	516.74	.775	21.53**
Negative Stereotypes	.801	.641	.007	5.43	-.084	-2.33*

A hierarchical regression revealed that Positive Stereotypes significantly predicted [Dependent Variable], accounting for 63.4% of the variance, $R^2 = .634$, $F(1, 298) = 516.74$, $p < .01$. The inclusion of Negative Stereotypes in the second step produced a small but significant increase in explained variance, $\Delta R^2 = .007$, F change = 5.43, $p < .05$. The final model explained 64.1% of the variance in [Dependent Variable]. Positive Stereotypes were a strong positive predictor ($\beta = .775$, $t = 21.53$, $p < .01$), whereas Negative Stereotypes were a weak but significant negative predictor ($\beta = -.084$, $t = -2.33$, $p < .05$).

Discussion

This study looked at how servant leadership, implicit attitudes, stereotypes, and procedural justice predict workers' mental health and quality of life. The results showed that the best predictor of quality of life, accounting for about 70% of the variation, was servant leadership, particularly authenticity and empowerment. These findings confirm earlier studies (Van Dierendonck & Nuijten, 2011; Hassan et al., 2023), emphasising the value of empowering, supporting leadership in raising worker satisfaction and quality of life.

Stereotypes, especially favourable ones, were found to be the most significant determinants of mental health. A substantial correlation was found between positive stereotypes and mental health, indicating that psychological resilience is strengthened by positive perceptions and supporting group identity. Negative stereotypes, on the other hand, had a minor but significant negative impact. According to Tajfel and Turner (1986), social identity theory highlights the influence of group-based ideas on psychological outcomes.

Although the effects were moderate, implicit attitudes—more especially, prejudices connected to surnames—also predicted both mental health and QOL. This implies that well-being can be subtly influenced by unconscious self-associations, such as those with one's social identity. The established relationship between fairness and satisfaction was confirmed by the substantial prediction of QOL by procedural justice (Colquitt, 2001).

Theoretical Implications; by fusing leadership and justice frameworks with implicit social cognition (implicit attitudes, stereotypes), the findings contribute to the field of organisational psychology. They draw attention to the various ways that leadership conduct, group views, and individual biases affect wellbeing.

Practical Implications; Training in servant leadership should be a top priority for organisations, with a focus on authenticity and empowerment. Reducing harmful stereotypes and unconscious biases may promote inclusivity and improve wellbeing. Equally important are policies that support procedural justice.

Limitations and Future Directions; Inference about causality is limited by the cross-sectional design. Response bias may be present in self-report data. Future research ought to use experimental or longitudinal designs and look into other factors, like organisational climate. Generalizability would also be improved by extending beyond Indian contexts.

Conclusion; This study offers solid proof that procedural justice, servant leadership, implicit attitudes, and stereotypes all influence employee well-being. Quality of life was significantly predicted by servant leadership, especially authenticity and empowerment. The strongest determinants of mental health were stereotypes, both positive and negative. Perceptions of justice and implicit attitudes also played a major role. In order to improve mental health and quality of life, these findings highlight the necessity of multi-level interventions in organisations, including cultivating inclusive cultures, training servant leaders, and guaranteeing procedural justice.

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